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Assessment Of Computerizing Land Registration Processes In Rivers State (A Case Study Of Port Harcourt Lands Registry)

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ABSTRACT

Rapid urban population in Nigeria, mostly in cities has made families to need thrice as much land as they need and as such increase land registration and documentation. This situation has given the government concern on how to improve urban development programs and strategies, causing urgent need for computerization of land titles registration so as to improve on proper documentation and storage. The study aim is to assess the activities of computerizing of land registration processes in Rivers State a case study of Port Harcourt lands registry. This study adopted the pragmatic research philosophy, the case study research design style was adopted and the study employed qualitative and quantitative research method. The targeted populations were government agencies such as Rivers State Ministry of Lands and Survey, and Rivers State Geographical information system (RIVGIS) which is a total of (160). Tools used in analyzing data were descriptive statistics, content/thematic analysis and data's were presented using text, tables and charts. The study revealed that there are four problems associated with analogue land registration system; seven activities of computerizing land title registration system, and five inadequacies of RIVGIS. The study recommends that effective professionals (with land administration knowledge) with competent, well equipped and a compact work force that will guarantee efficiency in honesty, transparency and quality services should be employed and finally government should provide and equip Survey department with current equipment that will match that of RIVGIS.

Keywords: Computerization of Land Title, Land Title Registration Processes, Analogue System,

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been rapid growth in urban areas which has put enormous pressure on lands acquisition in Rivers State. Based on the National population commission Port Harcourt regarded 832,471 population in 1996, but the interim figure for the 2006 national census shows that Port Harcourt has increased in population over one million (Temova, 2017). Rivers State is still growing and with this alarming increase in population most of the residence, families need thrice as much land as they did in two decades. Land is fixed and as such people are forced to make use of every strip of land whether planned or unplanned (Ohochukwu and Adibe, 2022). This situation gave the Government the need to look at its urban development program and strategies, thereby causing an urgent need for computerizing land registration processes for proper documentation and accessibility.

The federal government of Nigeria in its white paper (National Urban Policy, 2006:45) observed that uncontrolled urban development brings tremendous difficulties coupled with getting access to register

land (NUP, 2014). The federal government of Nigeria has said that the main objective of urban development policy is to ensure that land is available and orderly developed in the urban areas (Nup, 1978). However, just like the federal government of Nigeria, the Rivers State government implemented this view by ensuring that all land in Rivers state are dully registered to ensure proper planning and this was done by creating a department called Rivers State Geographical Information System (RIVGIS). Similarly, it is observed that computerizing land related data in many states in Nigeria has been a very contentious issues, nevertheless it have also been a welcome development in many States. Although lack of computerization of land related data has resulted to conflict of interest between landowners and government, land speculators and landlords on ground which is due to the analogue system of land registration. In this view of the implication of analogue system, it has inspired this study to underscore the computerization of land title registration processes in Rivers State.

1.2. Aim and Objective of the Study

Aim of the study is to assess the activities of computerizing of land registration processes in Rivers State a case study of Port Harcourt lands registry.

Therefore, the objectives of the study are as follows:

- I. To identify the problems of analogue system of land title registration in the study area
- II. To examine the activities of computerizing land title registration process in the study area
- III. To determine the inadequacies of employing RIVGIS

2. Theoretical Framework

Land instrument registration is a means by which data relating to a piece of land such as ownership, size, location, encumbrances etc, are kept in the public registry for the use of anyone (Thakur, Dutta, Khadanga and Venkatesh, 2005 cited by Ullah and Hussain, 2023). Land title registration started as far back as the coming of the colonial masters, although the Land use Act of March 29, 1978 chapter 2002 of the law of the Federation of Nigeria 1990 divested land ownership from individuals to states and Federal Government (Otubu, 2018). The Act gave rise to increase in demand for land title registration to determine who owns a particular piece of land at a particular time. Land title registration ensures efficient transfer and protection of ownership/right over land, it is a means that government offers security to tenure, it helps to regulate land markets and implement land reforms to enhance land value (Babalola, and Hull, 2019).

Furthermore, land title registration process in Nigeria is governed by the Land Registration Act No. 36 of 1924 and other enactment in some states of the federation (Abraham, 2023). In Rivers State, land instrument registration is governed by the land instrument of 1925 (Cap 72) and land instrument registration law of Rivers State (Onyebuchi and Kakulu, 2022). Section 6 of the land instrument registration law, (Cap 74) of Rivers state requires all land matters including power of attorney affecting land to be registered at the Land registry(Kachella .v. Bank 2001 10 NWLR721 422)

According to Surv. C.E. Oboli (FNIS) Director, Cadastral Surveyes and Surv. A. O. Akpoyoware (Mnis) Assistant Chief Surveyor, office of the Federation OSGOF) on a paper presented on the status of land records system and its relevance to infrastructural development in Nigeria; that the federal republic of Nigeria has an area of 923,768KM, but has large scale map of less than 3%, which is due to lack of proper land title registration. Although it was understood that activities of land with inadequate registration and documentation leads to poor land stylization, some cases distortion of master plan in cities and this results to demolition of costly mansions.

2.1 Analogue system of land instrument registration in Rivers State

Section 2 of the land title registration law, define land instruments as documents affecting land whereby one party the grantor confers, transfers limits charges or extinguishes in favor of another the grantee, any right or title to land includes an Estate contract and a certificate of purchase. These instruments include:

- I. Building lease

- II. Deed of conveyance
- III. Lease agreement
- IV. Deed of assignment
- V. Deed of transfer
- VI. Deed of gift
- VII. Letters of administration
- VIII. Customer right of Occupancy
- IX. Deed of mortgage
- X. Memorandum of agreement
- XI. Power of attorney
- XII. Certificate of occupancy

However, the above mentioned instruments can be registered in the Lands registry, although since the enactment of the Land use Act of 1978, Certificate of Occupancy is the generally recognized title. A holder of this tile can transfer his interest to anyone who purchases the land or property from him/her. This is the reason why state governments develop efficient lands registries where such transfers are centrally registered for the notice of the general public (Researchers view).

Although, until very recently the Rivers State Lands Registry has operated in Analogue basis which is paper based as data are kept in sheets of paper which are arranged in files and folders called “volumes”. They are stored in shelves, wooden and metal cabinets and are held together in ropes. When a transaction is completed and signed by the Governor or authorized officer, hr ends the file to the Ministry of Lands who through the commissioner of Lands directs the Deed Registrar to register it. A summary of the basic processes of analogue registration is presented below in a chart.

Source: Ministry of Lands and Survey

2.1.1 *Difficulties of analogue system of land registration*

According to the office of Rivers State Registry the following are the difficulties of analogue system of land registration in Nigeria

- a) **Operations are papers:** paper based documents are subject to destruction by water, fire and insects, especially where it is piled up in heaps
- b) **Cannot detect multiple allocations:** analogue system cannot identify mutilation as there is no equipment to detect already registered piece of land or a survey that has been registered
- c) **Misplacement of document:** in the analogue system an important document can be carelessly misplaced or whole registrar can be misplaced and this constitutes problem.
- d) **Alteration in the documents:** alteration can easily be made in the property card or day book or even in the instrument itself to suit those in a law suit that patronized fraudsters in the Deed Registry.

2.2 *Computerization of land title registration using (RIVGIS)*

The need for a change from analogue land title registration in Rivers State Ministry of Lands and Survey gave birth to Rivers State Geographical Information (RIVGIS), a computer based data management system that contains both geometric cadastral information and property information with respect to land ownership. This project was conceived from the need to have a correct, reliable, easy and quick access to land registration and cadastral survey information. The project was introduced to the ministry in Public Private Partnership (PPE) initiative of the state administration with Ministry of Lands and Survey Port Harcourt and indigenous firm-megatech earth digital system limited.

The system was established to generate revenue for the state government by ensuring efficient revenue collection and administration. Also to cause high staff productivity level through training capacity building, thirdly to provide easy access to land ownership information in the state by multiple users, fourthly to provide the land market with information on ownership and location of property as needed by the public.

2.2.1 *Activities of computerization of land title registration using RIVGIS*

According to the office of the directorate of the Ministry of Land and Survey Rivers State, the following are the activities of computerizing land title registration using RIVGIS:

- a) **Charting of Survey Plan:** this involves accurately determining the location of every parcel of land on survey plans in Rivers State within seconds. This process is used for the benefit of land registration purposes.
- b) **Provision of Geographical Information and Satellite Imagery:** it provides satellite imagery, aerial photograph and geospatial information for the use of the Rivers State Government and other development agencies in physical planning.
- c) **Maps and Mapping:** provides textual and graphic data on Rivers state such as local government maps and boundaries, soil mapping and survey etc.
- d) **Title Search:** facilitate title search and verification in seconds from anywhere in the world via internet.
- e) **Ground Rent Administration:** ensures speedy calculation of ground rents and generate ground rent demand notices for any registered property within minutes and at any time.
- f) **Certificate of Occupancy Processing:** provides a foolproof step by step sequence of the title and survey plan authentication before the preparation of Certificate of Occupancy within 45 days
- g) **Re-Certification:** it will utilize the indexed, scanned, parcel-linked and digital land owner's records it has developed as the basis for re-issuance of new, durable and secure Certificate of Occupancy to genuine holders of Title to Land in Rivers State.

2.2.2 *Benefits of computerizing land title registration*

The following are the benefit of computerizing land title registration in Rivers State:

- a) **Reduction in the rate of corruption:** there is reduction in the rate of corruption with the introduction of computer as there is no room for alterations, forgery, misplacement, removal of important documents from the registry because every information is computerized.
- b) **Staff training in information technology:** it helped in the training of staff of Ministry of Lands and Survey in the use of information technology, which is a rule and procedure that all staff will be familiar with before working on the computer effectively.
- c) **Productivity of staff:** it has helped staff to do their job effectively, make job processing less time consuming and work treated with less mistakes.
- d) **Detailed information of every transaction:** in a computerized system of land title registration, every registered land is stored in the system for easy references. The survey plan, the location of the property, and every other transaction about the property.
- e) **Better documentation:** computerization is a source of capturing, storing, checking, analyzing, and displaying data. Therefore, it makes documentation easy because many jobs are no longer done manually.

2.3 *Inadequacies of Rivers State Geographical information system (RIVGIS)*

In course of the computerization of land title registration, the following inadequacies were found from RIVGIS:

- a) **Charting:** there are usually differences in the surveys done by the Survey Department of RIVGIS and the Ministry of Lands and Survey as there is difference in coordinates. This is because RIVGIS wants all survey submitted to bear their own coordinates and this lead to delay in job execution.
- b) **Non-involvement of staff of Ministry of lands and survey in the project:** the end users of the project (RIVGIS) which is Ministry of Land and Survey are not fully involved in the project, rather, RIVGIS employs unprofessional and inexperienced staff.
- c) **Lack of photocopies of removed files in the ministry to RIVGIS:** the removal of files from the Ministry of Lands and Survey without duplicate/photocopy is a big challenge especially for those in the registry department.
- d) **Non provision of website to facilitate e-marketing:** this is one of the promises that was made initially from RIVGIS but up till now it has not been fulfilled.
- e) **Duplication of staff functions:** as RIVGIS employ a different body, they have taken over the functions of lands officers in government services thereby abandoning their mission.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the pragmatic research philosophy, the case study research design style was adopted and the study employed qualitative and quantitative research method. Qualitative data was collected through interviews from key informants including government officials, official documents, and personal observation. Quantitative data was collected through review on land registration processes and the acts governing the federation. The targeted populations were government agencies such as Rivers State Ministry of Lands and Survey, and Rivers State Geographical information system (RIVGIS). Tools used in analyzing data were descriptive statistics, content/thematic analysis and data's were presented using text, tables and charts.

3. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study is to figure out the activities of computerization of land title registration and its benefits. The study investigated the difficulties that are associated with analogue system of land registration, also the activities of land title registration in rivers state in the case of RIVGIS and to make recommendation that help improve land administration and registration processes.

The questionnaires were developed based on the reviews, archives and interviews. The respondents were asked to fill up the questionnaires in accordance with the level of agreement based on their experiences. The survey was sent via email to the staffs in the ministry of land and survey, RIVGIS staffs and other agencies involved in land registration processes for 170 respondents. One sixty (160) out of 170 answered the questionnaire and sent it back via email. Five were interviewed face to face by verbal conversation. Therefore, the respondent's ratio of this study was 94%.

3.1 Difficulties in analogue system of land instrument registration in the study area

3.1.1 Agreement level on the difficulties in analogue system of land instrument registration in the study area

Figure 3.1.1 Agreement level on the difficulties in using analogue system

Source: Research data, (2025)

The respondent's ratio for this question is 98% (157 respondents out of 160) said yes, that there are difficulties in using analogue system of land registration processes in the study area, while 2% (3 respondents out of 160) said no. hence the survey shows that there are difficulties in using analogue land registration.

3.1.2 Difficulties of analogue system of land instrument registration

The study sought to establish the problem that is associated with the practice of analogue system of land title registration in Rivers State. Findings in figure 3.1.2 show that above half of the respondents strongly agree that the four problems (*operations are papers, cannot detect multiple allocation, misplacement of document and alteration in the document*) that are listed in the figure below are the difficulties that are associated with analogue system of land registration. The respondent added that this system of land title registration takes longer time before document is registered, encourages corruption and consumes a lot of money from the owner.

Figure 3.1.2 Difficulties of analogue system of land instrument registration
 Source: Research data, (2025)

3.2 Computerization of land title registration using (RIVGIS) in the study area

The study sought to establish the activities of computerization of land registration system, which the study showed that there are six different things that are done using computer in land title registration. All the respondents agreed and strongly agreed that the six listed activities (*charting of survey plan, maps and mapping, certificate of occupancy, ground rent administration, re-certification and title search*) below, are done using computer in the ministry of lands and survey. Similarly, majority of the respondents stated that these activities are flexible, it facilities job delivery. However, sometimes Nigerian networks are bad and this reduces work speed and delivery.

Figure 3.2 Activities of computerization of land title registration
 Source: Research data, (2025)

3.2.1 Benefits of computerized land title registration than analogue system.

Respondents in the study were asked to indicate the benefits to which computerizing land title registration system benefits land registration than analogue system. Findings in figure 3.2.1 shows that vast majority (99%) of respondents indicated that computerizing land title registration has more benefits than the analogue system with (1%) of the respondent indicating that it doesn't have more benefits. The respondents cited (*reduction in the rate of corruption, staff training in information technology, productivity of staff, detailed information of every transaction, better documentation*) as the benefits of computerizing land title registration processes.

Figure 3.2.1 computerizing system more beneficial than analogue system
Source: Research data (2025)

3.3 Inadequacies of Rivers State Geographical information system (RIVGIS)

Respondents in the study area were asked to indicate their level of agreement on the inadequacies of RIVGIS. Findings in figure 3.3 show that the vast majority (95%) of respondents indicated that there are five inadequacies (*different survey no, non-involvement if ministry staff, lack of photocopies before the transfer of file, no website provision, duplication of staff functions*) of RIVGIS.

Figure 3.3 Inadequacies of RIVGIS
Source: Research data (2025)

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Computerization of land title registration process makes work less cumbersome, as it puts to rest permanently to inconveniences encountered by the analogue system of land title registration processes. the RIVGIS project has seen to have helped solve most problems encountered during land registration by putting to rest anxiety expressed by individuals, consultants, clients of various governmental and private agencies and private agencies as to the process of the registration of their land tiles as well as the preservation of necessary particulars with respect to their landed properties. From the above, the study recommends that:

- a) In order to streamline survey activities between th Ministry and RIVGIS, there should be an extensive restructuring of the survey department to enable accurate charting this means that the government should provide and equip the Survey Department with the current survey equipment that will match that of RIVGIS.
- b) Non-involvement of the staff of the Ministry of Lands and Survey in this project has led to the misinterpretation of most data. Therefore, there is a need for the RIVGIS project to involve the staff of Ministry of Lands and Survey for ideas as the end-users of the projects.
- c) RIVGIS charts every survey plan submitted for fie opening to know whether that particular land have being giving number before, in this way multiple file numbering can be checked.
- d) RIVGIS should ensure that photocopies of all files it uses in its exercise are left for the use of the Ministry.
- e) Professionals on land administration with computer knowledge should be recruited for better productivity and efficiency.
- f) Consultants should try and keep to their terms and agreement by providing website as this will make land transaction and land registration easier for land owners and intended buyers.

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